

Development and Evaluation of Mechanical Properties for Carbon Fabric / Phenolic Composites with Injection Molding

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1 Introduction

Phenolic resin has excellent properties of heat-resistance, low smoke and combustion resistance in fire and these properties is suitable to be employed as a matrix of composites used in the structures of railway carriages and aircrafts. However a resole type of phenolic resin (resole resin) has high viscosity, we use its dilution to decrease its viscosity with water or solvent for the handling. Moreover, the resole resin generates water formed from the condensation reaction. The water remained in the matrix causes voids after molding. As a result, the strength of phenolic composite varies widely owing to the voids.

On the other hand, a novolak type of phenolic resin (novolak resin) is used for small sizes of products, such as electric parts by injection molding. The novolak resin becomes to be hard by the addition of hardening agent and it is melted with a heater in the cylinder of injection machine and, the melted novolak resin containing short fibers is injected to the metal die. In this method, the fine matrix without voids can be obtained but higher strength and stiffness of composites can't be expected because the short fibers used as the reinforcement become shorter during the process of premixing with resin.

The authors developed a method of injection molding for fabrication a new type of phenolic FRP [1-2]. This FRP was composed of the novolak resin as a matrix and glass fibers (GF) fabrics and carbon fibers (CF) fabrics as a reinforcement. However, according to the results of tensile test, the phenolic resin / CF fabrics composite showed the weak interface. It was thought that the sizing agent to be treated to the surface of the present carbon fibers seemed to be improper to the phenolic resin at the interface. Therefore, the effect of the sizing agent on the interface strength between the phenolic resin and the CF fabrics should be made clear.

It was reported that the increase of resin toughness is expected to prevent the delamination of CFRP [3-4] and that the toughness of matrix near the interface in the GFRP was improved by using silane coupling (S.C) agent [5].

The purpose of this paper is to increase tensile strength due to the brake of fibers. Therefore, the removal of sizing agent from the surface of the CFRP was devised and the toughness of novolak resin near the interface region was improved by the treatment of the S.C. In addition, the tensile properties of phenolic resin / CF fabrics composites were compared with those of the conventional vinyl ester resin / CF fabrics composite.

2 Outline of the Injection Molding

2.1 Material

Two mixture rates with two kinds of novolak resin were used here as a matrix, one mixture rate was a high molecular weight of 68 % and low molecular weight of 22 wt% (Type 1). Another was the high molecular weight of 66 % and the low molecular weight of 24 % (Type 2) and the two types were also mixed with 10wt% of Hexamine of hardening agent. Then, the mixed powders were pressed under 10MPa for producing a cylinder form and it was broken for producing a form of pellets. The reinforcement used here was 2 sheets of CF fabrics.

2.2 Molding Technique

An injection molding machine is shown in Figure 1. In order to avoid the brake of fibers with the screw in the cylinder and then to obtain a stronger phenolic composite by the reinforcement of longer fibers, a technique of the RTM molding was introduced. The fabrics composed of long carbon fibers were beforehand placed in the metal die. Next, the melted novolak pellets with the hardener and

additive were injected to the metal die as shown in Figure 2. The conditions of injection molding are listed in Table 1. Under these conditions, the after curing time was executed for 1 hour at the temperature of 150 °c .

Fig.1 Schematic view of injection molding

Fig.2 Shape and sizes of metal die

Table 1 Injection molding of conditions

Cylinder Temperature [°C]	80
Die Temperature [°C]	150
Injection Speed [mm/s]	7.3
Cure Time [min]	5

3. Removal of sizing agent

3.1 Method

Since the sizing agent of CF gave the bad effects on the interface strength, the sizing agent was removed by using a sulfate method according to JIS R 7604. In this method, the mass of specimen (m) was about 5g and the sizing content was calculated the following equation.

$$S = \frac{m - m_d}{m_d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

In which m_d was the mass after the removal of sizing agent. Since there was a risk to use the sulfate method for the large size of CF fabrics, a pyrolysis method (JISK7604) under the temperature of 380 °C in a muffle furnace was used and its combustion hours were decided by the comparison of the sulfate method.

3.2 Results of sizing agent release

Figure 3 shows the result of the sulfate method and also shows the results of the pyrolysis method according to the changes of combustion hours. From 1 hour to 3 hours, the sizing content was under 1.7% and these hours were insufficient to remove the sizing agent. Otherwise, the over 5 hours showed the excess of sizing content. The sizing agent was not only removed but also the CF defected and the strength of CF seemed to be down. As a result, the combustion hour was decided to 4 hours and the sizing content at 4 hours was same as the result of sulfate method.

Fig.3 Relation of sizing agent release between Time

4. Application of silane coupling agent

After the sizing agent was removed from the surface of CF fabrics, a silane coupling agent (KBM 903 of Amino base, Shinetsu Silicone Co. Ltd) was used to the CF fabrics in order to increase the interface toughness between the CF and the novolak resin.

The CF fabrics were soaked into the S.C diluted with ethanol (ethanol 99 vol. % and silane coupling agent 1 vol. %) and then the soaked CF fabrics were

dried for 10 minutes under the temperature of 100 °C. After the silane coupling treatment, the CF fabrics were also treated with resole coating.

5. Tensile test

5.1 Specimen

For avoiding the effect of inlet hole as shown in Figure 2, the specimens were cut down from the right and the left sides of the phenolic CF fabrics specimen except its middle part with a precision sawing machine. The dimension of specimen is shown in Figure 4. Both ends of the specimen were bonded with the GFRP tabs and the condition of the static tensile experiment was executed under the tensile speed of 1mm/min and the room temperature.

Fig.4 Dimension of specimen (unit :mm)

In order to demonstrate the performance of the phenolic / CF fabrics developed here, their tensile strength was compared with that of vinyl ester resin / CF fabrics. The vinyl ester resin / CF fabrics was fabricated with two sheets of CF fabrics same as the phenolic CF fabrics under the pressure and the temperature (a hot press molding) combined with a vacuum method.

5.2 Tensile test

The mean values of five specimens for the tensile strengths of Type 1 with and without the S.C, and Type 2 with S.C, and the vinyl ester / CF fabrics composite under room temperatures are listed in Table 2. The fiber volume fraction of all of the specimens was same value of 41%. The typical stresses to strain curves of tensile test are shown in Figure 5. According to the results of tensile test, the tensile strength and the Young's modulus of Type 1 without S.C were

smaller than those of Type 1 and 2 with S.C because the break of carbon fibers were not observed in Type 1 without S.C (Figure 6). Otherwise, the breaks of carbon fibers were observed in Type 1 and Type 2 with S.C (Figure 7~8). This reason was that the interface strength between the phenolic resin and the CF fabrics increased due to the silane coupling (S.C) agent. However the strength and Young's modulus of vinyl ester resin / CF fabrics showed the highest values among the 4 specimens due to the better impregnation of resin to the CF fabrics compared with the phenolic /CF fabrics composite. This better impregnation presented the separation of specimen in the tensile test due to the full brake (Figure 9) Since the phenolic resin could easily penetrate into the CF fabrics in the specimen of Type 2 (Figure 10) with S.C compared with the specimen of Type 1 with S.C (Figure 11), the strength and Young's modulus of Type 2 with S.C was higher than those of Type 1 with S.C.

Table 2 Result of tensile test

	Tensile strengt		Young's modulus	
	Ave.[MPa]	Standard deviation[%]	Ave.[Gpa]	Standard deviation[%]
vinyl ester CFRP	936	7.5	56.2	8.32
Type 1 without S.C	679	0.707	44.0	5.2
Type 1 with S.C	770	4.15	47.1	7.49
Type 2 with S.C	818	3.15	48.9	6.08

Fig.5 Tensile stress-strain curves fourth specimens under room temperature

However, the impregnation of vinyl ester composite (Figure 12) was better than that of Type 2 with S.C. In order to increase the strength and stiffness of phenolic resin/CF fabrics, the mixture ratio of high

molecular to low molecular in the phenolic resin will be examined because the mixture ratio contributes to improve the penetration of phenolic resin into inside of the carbon fabrics.

6 Conclusions

- 1) The strength and stiffness of phenolic/CF fabrics with the surface treatment of silane coupling agent showed the higher values compared with those without the surface treatment because of improving their interface strength.
- 2) It was clear that the mixture ratio of the high molecular to the low molecular in the phenolic resin influenced the strength and Young's modulus of phenolic/CF fabrics composite.

Fig.6 Fracture side view of Type 1 without S.C

Fig.7 Fracture side view of Type 2 with S.C

Fig.8 Fracture side view of Type 2 with S.C

Fig.9 Side view of Vinyl ester CFRP

Fig.10 Cross section of specimen of Type 2 with S.C

Fig.11 Cross section of specimen of Type 1 with S.C

Fig.12 Cross section of specimen of Vinyl ester CFRP

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